

Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometric Determination of Molybdenum(VI) after Adsorption of its 1-Hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea Complex on Microcrystalline Naphthalene

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An atomic absorption spectrophotometric (AAS) method has been developed for the determination of Mo^{VI} after adsorption of its 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea complex on microcrystalline naphthalene. Analytical applications of thiourea and substituted thioureas have been reported earlier¹. The complexation between hydroxy substituted thioureas and metal ions is due to the oxime and thio-keto groups which interact with molybdenum forming a coloured complex. Numerous methods have been developed for the determination of Mo^{VI} by AAS² in many organic and inorganic materials including steels.

A stable water-insoluble complex of Mo^{VI} and reagent is formed which is quantitatively adsorbed on microcrystalline naphthalene from aqueous phase in the pH range 1.8–4.2. The adsorbed crystals are separated by filtration, dried and dissolved in dimethylformamide. The absorbance is measured at 313.3 nm by AAS. Adsorption is very fast at 40–50°. Ten samples of the solution containing 30.0 µg Mo^{VI} were prepared by the recommended procedure, affording a mean absorbance of 0.341 with a relative standard deviation of 0.67%. Beer's law is obeyed over the concentration range 2.5–40.0 µg of Mo in 10 ml dimethylformamide solution. The sensitivity was found to be 0.0087 µg cm⁻² of Mo for 1% absorption. The proposed method has been successfully applied to the rapid determination of molybdenum in steel (EN-24, EN-25 containing certified value 0.28 and 0.53% Mo respectively, obtained 0.28 ± 0.01 and 0.53 ± 0.02% Mo respectively). The result shows that values obtained are in the good agreement with the certified values. The possible interferences due to the presence of various di-

verse metal ions, i.e. Mg^{II}, Ca^{II}, Mn^{II}, Pb^{II}, Cu^{II}, Co^{II}, Zn^{II}, Fe^{II}, Al^{III}, Cr^{III}, Ti^{IV}, V^V and W^{VI} were observed.

Experimental

A standard stock solution of Mo^{VI} (1000 µg ml⁻¹) was prepared by dissolving ammonium heptamolybdate tetrahydrate in distilled water. A 0.2% solution of 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea was prepared in ethanol. A 20% naphthalene solution was prepared in acetone. Buffer solution was prepared by mixing equal volume of 1 M acetic acid and 1 M ammonium acetate for pH 2.8–4.2. All chemicals used were of spectrograde quality.

A Perkin-Elmer 2380 atomic absorption spectrophotometer was used. pH was measured on a Systronics 335 pH meter.

Procedure An aliquot (containing 2.5–40.0 µg of Mo) from a standard sample solution was diluted with distilled water (60 ml), and adjusted to pH 3.5 and acetate buffer solution (3 ml) was added followed by 0.2% 1-hydroxy-1,3-diphenyl-2-thiourea solution (2.5 ml). After mixing the contents, it was heated on a water-bath at 40–50° for about 15 min. Then 20% naphthalene solution (3 ml) was added and shake vigorously for 2 min. The molybdenum complex was adsorbed on microcrystalline naphthalene, filtered the solid dried in an oven at 50° and then dissolve in dimethylformamide. The solution was aspirated into nitrous oxide-acetylene flame and the absorbance at 313.3 nm using a molybdenum hollow cathode lamp by AAS against reagent blank.

References

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